

Proposal of a telehealth system for a large-scale public hospital in Minas Gerais

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Abstract — This article describes the development of a telehealth system for a large-scale public hospital located in the state of Minas Gerais (Brazil) to reduce travelling from small to big cities in order to get medical assistance. The software offers two types of access: one for the patients and other, with enhanced access, for the medical staff. This distinction ensures distinct functionalities for each user, thereby maintaining the security of patient data. The system, developed using Flutter and integrated with Firebase, enables real-time management of physician schedules and provides access to patient medical records. The project incorporates features like online booking and automated notifications to streamline the care process. The results until this moment show the interfaces with different level of access, besides the different features presented for each kind of user. A functional application has been successfully developed. For future work, we plan to implement a beta test to identify potential issues related to usability and functionality. This process aims to optimize the application based on feedback from its final users.

Palavras-chave — *telehealth, public hospital, Minas Gerais, Flutter.*

I. Introduction

Telemedicine, particularly telehealth, has proven to be a promising tool in transforming healthcare services by expanding access and optimizing resource management [1]. In this context, the present study aims to develop a system and analyze the implementation of this telehealth application in a large-scale Healthcare Facility (HF) in the state of Minas Gerais, in addition to discussing the challenges and opportunities encountered in this process.

The scientific literature has shown the potential of teleconsultation across various clinical scenarios, including the

follow-up of chronic patients, demand triage, and the delivery of specialized consultations. Studies from other hospitals, as evidenced in [2][3][4][5], have demonstrated significant benefits, such as a high rate of care provision for patients, resulting in advantages for both users and teleconsultants.

Nonetheless, implementing a teleconsultation system presents several challenges, including the need for proper infrastructure, training healthcare professionals, guaranteeing data security, and adapting existing workflows.

Given this scenario, this paper presents a proposal for a teleconsultation system to be implemented in a large-scale hospital, using modern and accessible technologies with a focus on responsiveness, scalability, and real-time integration. Furthermore, it also seeks to discuss the characteristics of usability, security, and the technical feasibility of adopting the solution in a public hospital context.

II. Methodology

Developed with the *Flutter Software Development Kit (SDK)*[6][7] and a VSCode extension, the teleconsultation system aims to create a web-based application with real-time database access. The main separation of access levels was established by creating distinct logins for physicians and patients, as depicted in Figure 1. This differentiation is essential as each user group has unique needs and specific functionalities. Consequently, during the registration process, physicians are required to provide their CRM register number (a mandatory identification code number for healthcare professionals in Brazil provided by the Regional Council of Medicine), whereas patients are only required to submit personal information and details relevant to their medical history.

Furthermore, additional features were conceived for both the physician and the patient users of this application. Physicians have the ability to make their teleconsultation

availability public to prospective patients, thereby enabling them to book appointments on specific dates and times. Patients, in turn, have the option to view their pending appointments as well as cancel them if they so desire.

The system's interface was initially designed using the *Figma*[8] platform to create a preliminary prototype. This allowed for the graphical visualization of the application's pages, which in turn streamlined the overall development process. Additionally, the software was developed with responsive features, meaning the interfaces automatically adapt to different screen types. This allows it to be used on computers, smartphones, and tablets of any brand.

Figure 1: Use case diagram

For data storage, the application's foundation was the implementation of a Firebase database (REF) for the collection and persistence of information. The Firebase system, a platform developed by Google, stores data in a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, structuring cloud-based databases and providing real-time synchronization to all connected devices [9]. Thus, the Firebase Realtime Database allows for the creation of advanced and collaborative applications, providing secure access directly from the client's code. Data is maintained locally and automatically synchronized when the device comes back online, offering a responsive experience. Security rules allow for defining how data can be accessed, with integration to Firebase Authentication for permission control. As a NoSQL database, it is optimized for fast and scalable operations, supporting millions of users without compromising real-time performance.

Another tool that supports the system's functionality is Deep Linking [10]. This is a crucial feature for accessing specific positions within an application, analogous to navigating between webpages or even embedded pages on a

standard computer. This logic was implemented in the rounds application, as each page of the app corresponds to a webpage that receives a specific link as an argument.

III. Results and Discussion

As depicted in Figure 2, the Login Screen's interface was designed to simplify user access to the system.

Figure 2: Login page

The physician's profile includes fields for CRM, specialty, and available consultation hours, which enables detailed control of their professional schedule and information (Figure 3). Conversely, the patient's profile requires information such as age, weight, height, and personal details (ID number and address), thereby creating a comprehensive record for their medical history.

Figure 3: Physician's register page

Figures 4 and 5 depict, respectively, the main interface for a physician's and a patient's account. A key distinction in access is evident on these pages: a physician is permitted to view all of their patients' records, as well as schedule/view future appointments (Figure 6) and request examinations individually. A patient, conversely, can only view their own consultation

history and upcoming appointments (Figure 7), along with any associated examinations and prescriptions.

Figure 4: Physician's account page

Figure 5: Patient's account page

Figure 6: Physician's future appointments page

Figure 7: Patient's upcoming appointments page

Upon registration, a physician gains access to a schedule displaying all their booked appointments. When a patient schedules a new time slot, it is automatically marked as unavailable to prevent conflicts and ensure organizational efficiency. Additionally, the physician is granted access to a preliminary version of the patient's Electronic Health Record (Figure 8), which currently serves as a foundational outline. While it allows for basic consultation and the addition of essential information, such as ICD-10 diagnostic codes and brief notes, its full functionality such as integration of detailed past consultations, test results, and treatment plans is envisioned for future development.

The image shows a mobile application interface for an electronic health record. At the top, there is a teal header with a back arrow and the text 'Prontuário Eletrônico'. Below the header is a light purple background. The main content area is a white rounded rectangle containing several input fields: 'Nome do paciente' (a large text box), 'Idade' (a small text box), 'Data ...' (a date picker), 'Peso ...' (a text box), 'Altura...' (a text box), 'RG' (a text box), 'Endereço' (a text box), 'Observações' (a large text area), and 'CID-10' (a text box). At the bottom of the white area is a teal rounded button labeled 'Concluir'.

Figure 8: Electronic health record

For patients, the appointment booking process will be straightforward and intuitive. They will be able to select the desired specialty, view a list of available physicians for that area, and choose the healthcare plan. As this paper focuses on a public hospital setting, the Unified Health System (SUS) will be the default system. Subsequently, the patient will define the date and time for the consultation. Upon confirmation, the system is expected to send a confirmation message via WhatsApp, providing practicality and ensuring all appointment details are received. This functionality, which may be implemented in the future using the automation tool n8n, will further enhance communication efficiency. Once this framework is fully implemented, it will enable a personalized experience, streamlining patient care and real-time information management.

IV. Conclusion

The developed application is simple and straightforward, ensuring that its use is uncomplicated for any type of user. It is important to emphasize that implementing this system in a large public hospital can benefit countless people, and when fully operational, it may even lead to a reduction in long queues for low-complexity appointments. Furthermore, continuous optimization of the application using data collected from beta testing is essential. The user experience, regardless of who the user is, serves as one of the most valuable sources of data for improving a system like the one described in this project. However, it is important to highlight that implementing a digital system is not free of challenges. The adoption of new technologies can face resistance from users, especially those who are accustomed to traditional working methods.

Currently, the project is still under active development, with efforts focused on fully integrating all proposed features. One of the main technical challenges involves implementing the communication protocol between the application and WhatsApp using the n8n automation platform. This functionality is crucial for enabling the automatic sending of appointment reminders, confirmations, and follow-up messages directly to patients through WhatsApp, a widely used and accessible communication tool. However, setting up secure and reliable message flows in n8n requires addressing several issues, including proper API token management, persistent session maintenance using the WhatsApp Business API or third-party gateways, handling message rate limits, and ensuring compliance with encryption and data protection standards.

Additionally, because message delivery and user interactions occur asynchronously, the system must include reliable error handling and detailed logging mechanisms to prevent communication failures. These requirements become even more complex when the system must scale to handle multiple users at the same time in a real hospital environment. Continuous testing, validation, and refinement are necessary to ensure the system remains stable, secure, and user-friendly, especially when dealing with sensitive healthcare data. Overcoming these technical and operational challenges is essential to deliver an effective and reliable digital healthcare solution.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

REFERENCES

- [1] SCHMITZ, Carlos André Aita, et al. Teleconsulta: nova fronteira da interação entre médicos e pacientes. *Revista brasileira de medicina de família e comunidade*. Vol. 12, n. 39 (jan./dez. 2017), p. 1-7., 2017.
- [2] FREITAS, L. de F. N. ; JACINTO, A. K. de L. ; FERNANDES, J. M. A. Telenursing: Implementation of Teleconsultations in a University Hospital. *Research, Society and Development, [S. l.]*, v. 13, n. 3, p. e14413345454, 2024. DOI: 10.33448/rsd-v13i3.45454. Disponível em: <https://rsdjournal.org/index.php/rsd/article/view/45454>. Acesso em: 21 oct. 2024.
- [3] SCUDELLER, Paula Gobi et al. Telemedicine in Brazil: teleconsultations at the largest University Hospital in the Country. *Telemedicine Reports*, v. 4, n. 1, p. 193-203, 2023.

- [4] YUN, Eun Kyoung; PARK, Hyeoun-Ae. Telenursing in Korea. In: Telenursing. London: Springer London, 2011. p.75-82.
- [5] DE ANDRADE FERREIRA, Ediane et al. The value of the nursing teleconsultation at the human milk bank in the view of nurses. *Revista de Enfermagem da UFSM*, v. 13, 2023.
- [6] NAGARAJ,K.; PRABAKARAN, B.; RAMKUMAR, M. O. Application development for a project using Flutter. In: 2022 3rd International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC). IEEE, 2022. p. 947-951.
- [7] FLUTTER. Install. [S. l.]: Flutter, [2025?]. Disponível em: <https://docs.flutter.dev/get-started/install>. Acesso em: 4 ago. 2025
- [8] FIGMA. Figma: Collaborative interface design tool. Disponível em: <https://www.figma.com/pt-br/>. Acesso em: 4 ago. 2025.
- [9] KHAWAS,C.;SHAH,P. Application of Firebase in An droid app development: a study. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, v. 179, n. 46, p. 49-53, 2018.
- [10] AZIM, T.; RIVA, O.; NATH, S. uLink: Enabling user defined deep linking to app content. In: Proceedings of the 14th Annual International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications, and Services, 2016, p. 305-318.